

Internet Addiction: A Study on College going Students of District Anantnag

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ABSTRACT

The current research paper explores the phenomenon of internet addiction among College going students of district Anantnag. The study which was descriptive in nature was conducted on 100 College going students belonging to five different colleges of district Anantnag. The students were sampled by using simple random technique (Lottery Method) whereas, colleges were purposively selected. Data were collected by using a standardized tool developed by Daman Deep Kaur Gulati, Dr. Jose J. Kurisunkal and Dr. Mamta Bakliwal 2021. The data were analyzed by using t-test. The major finding of the study revealed that Internet Addiction is more in Arts Stream Students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag as compared to Science stream students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag.

Key Words: Internet Addiction, Lottery Method, t-test.

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INTRODUCTION

In the modern digital age, the internet has become an integral and indispensable component of daily life for billions of people around the world. What was once considered a novel technological innovation has rapidly evolved into an essential tool for communication, information-gathering, entertainment, and a multitude of other functions. The Internet's pervasive presence and increasingly ubiquitous accessibility through smartphones, laptops, tablets, and other digital devices have transformed the way individuals interact with the world and each other.

The ubiquity of the internet in the 21st century has ushered in a technological revolution, profoundly shaping the way we work, learn, socialize, and entertain ourselves. The internet has become an essential resource for a vast array of daily activities, from professional tasks and academic research to personal communication and leisure pursuits. It has enabled instantaneous access to a wealth of information, fostered global connectivity, and revolutionized the way we consume and share content.

However, as the internet has become more deeply embedded in the fabric of modern society, a concerning trend has emerged - the growing problem of problematic internet use and internet addiction. Internet addiction, characterized by an inability to control one's use of the internet despite the presence of negative consequences, has emerged as a significant public health concern in recent decades. As individuals, particularly young people, find themselves spending more and more time online, the detrimental effects of this excessive and compulsive internet use on mental health, physical well-being, social relationships, academic or occupational performance, and overall quality of life have become increasingly apparent.

Nature and Scope of Internet Addiction

In order to fully understand the issue of internet addiction, it is essential to first explore the definition and conceptualization of this behavioural disorder. Internet addiction, also referred to as problematic internet use or compulsive internet use, has been the subject of extensive research and debate among scholars and clinicians in recent decades.

The term "internet addiction" was first introduced in the 1990s by Dr. Ivan Goldberg, a psychiatrist who observed patterns of excessive and uncontrolled internet use among his patients. Goldberg proposed that individuals could become addicted to the internet, experiencing symptoms similar to those associated with substance addictions, such as tolerance, withdrawal, and impaired function in daily life. Since then, a growing body of research has sought to further define and characterize this emerging behavioural addiction.

One of the key challenges in defining internet addiction lies in the fact that the internet is not a single, discrete activity, but rather a platform that enables a wide range of activities, from social media and online gaming to e-commerce and information-seeking. As such, internet addiction is often conceptualized as a multidimensional construct, with various sub-types or "addictions" related to specific

internet-enabled behaviours, such as social media addiction, online gaming addiction, or cybersex addiction.

Despite this complexity, researchers have proposed various frameworks and diagnostic criteria for internet addiction. One of the most widely recognized models is the Generalized Problematic Internet Use Scale (GPIUS), developed by Caplan and colleagues. This model posits that internet addiction is characterized by a cognitive-behavioural syndrome, including symptoms such as mood regulation, compulsive use, cognitive preoccupation, and negative outcomes.

Another influential framework is the Internet Addiction Test (IAT), developed by Dr. Kimberly Young. The IAT assesses the degree of preoccupation, compulsive use, withdrawal symptoms, and negative consequences associated with problematic internet use. This assessment tool has been widely used in both clinical and research settings to identify and measure the severity of internet addiction.

It is important to note that the classification and diagnosis of internet addiction remain subject to on-going debate and refinement. While the American Psychological Association (APA) has recognized "Internet Gaming Disorder" as a condition warranting further study in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), the broader concept of internet addiction has not yet been formally included as a distinct diagnostic category. However, many researchers and clinicians advocate for the recognition of internet addiction as a legitimate behavioural addiction, akin to substance use disorders or gambling addiction.

Risk Factors and Etiological Mechanisms of Internet Addiction

The development of internet addiction is a complex and multifaceted process, influenced by a variety of individual, social, and environmental factors. Understanding the underlying risk factors and etiological mechanisms that contribute to the emergence and maintenance of this behavioural disorder is essential for designing effective prevention and intervention strategies.

Individual Factors :

A growing body of research has identified several individual-level factors that may predispose individuals to the development of internet addiction. Personality traits, such as high levels of impulsivity, sensation-seeking, and neuroticism, have been consistently linked to an increased risk of problematic internet use. Individuals with these characteristics may be more likely to engage in compulsive and excessive online behaviours as a means of mood regulation or stimulation-seeking.

Additionally, the presence of co-occurring mental health conditions, such as depression, anxiety, and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), has been associated with a higher likelihood of internet addiction. These underlying psychological and neurological factors may contribute to a heightened vulnerability to the development of addictive behaviours, including problematic internet use.

Demographic factors, such as age and gender, have also been identified as risk factors for internet addiction. Adolescents and young adults, particularly males, have consistently been found to be more susceptible to developing internet addiction. This

may be partially attributed to the developmental changes and social pressures experienced during these life stages, as well as the increased accessibility and pervasiveness of digital technologies among younger generations.

Social and Environmental Factors

Beyond individual-level characteristics, social and environmental factors also play a significant role in the etiology of internet addiction. The quality and nature of an individual's interpersonal relationships and social support systems can influence the risk of developing problematic internet use. For instance, individuals with poor social skills, limited social connections, or dysfunctional family environments may be more likely to turn to the internet as a means of socialization, emotional regulation, or escape from real-world problems.

The availability and accessibility of the internet, as well as the design and features of digital platforms and applications, can also contribute to the development of internet addiction. The ubiquity of smartphones and the constant connectivity they provide, combined with the reinforcing and addictive design elements of social media, online gaming, and other internet-based activities, can foster compulsive and excessive use.

Moreover, cultural and societal factors, such as the normalization of technology use, the perceived importance of online presence and participation, and the lack of digital literacy and self-regulation skills, can also shape an individual's relationship with the internet and increase the risk of problematic use.

Neuro-biological and Psychological Processes

In addition to the individual, social, and environmental factors, researchers have also explored the potential Neuro-biological and psychological mechanisms underlying internet addiction. Emerging evidence suggests that the neurological and Neuro-chemical processes involved in the development of substance addictions may also play a role in the etiology of internet addiction.

Studies have found that excessive internet use and engagement in certain online activities, such as gaming or social media use, can trigger the release of dopamine and other reward-related neurotransmitters in the brain's reward system. This can lead to a heightened sense of pleasure and reinforcement, potentially fuelling compulsive and addictive behaviours.

Furthermore, the cognitive and behavioural patterns associated with internet addiction, such as attentional biases, cognitive preoccupation, and impaired self-regulation, may be underpinned by specific psychological processes. These include the development of maladaptive coping strategies, distorted cognitions related to the internet and its use, and impaired executive functioning and impulse control.

By understanding the multifaceted risk factors and etiological mechanisms involved in the development of internet addiction, researchers and clinicians can better inform the design and implementation of targeted prevention and intervention strategies. This comprehensive approach is crucial for addressing the growing public health concern of problematic internet use in the digital age.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Various research studies have been conducted by various research scholars across the globe on internet addiction. Few of them have been presented below in chronological order;

In the study by Menon, Shanker & Narayanan, Lakshmi & Kahwaji, Ahmad (2018), the researchers investigated the internet addiction among college students. The study was conducted on 300 students in a management institute in India, where 300 students (first, second and third years' students) were sampled and the result shows that the older students were more internet addicted than the younger students. It also showed that men were more addicted than women.

A cross sectional study was conducted by Prashant Bagdey, Hemant Adikane, Uday Narlawar, Dadasaheb Dhage, Kishor Surwase, Alka Kaware (2018) for investigating the association between mental health and internet addiction among college students in Nagpur city. The result showed that the students aged from 17-25 years were high on internet addiction. They suggested that excessive use of the Internet effects on physical, mental health and social well-being of students.

A cross sectional study on internet addiction and their relationship with depression among professional college students was carried out by Subhashini KJ, Praveen G (2018). The study was conducted on 300 students from Hassan Institute of Medical Sciences (Government Medical College) and Government Engineering College, Karnataka. They found that out of 300 students 173 (57.7%) were found to be internet addicted and 67 (38.7%) among them were found to be depressed and a there was positive relation between internet and depression. A male student shows more internet addiction than female students.

Azher, Musarrat (2018) has explored the relationship between Internet Addiction and Anxiety among 300 PG students from University of Sargodha. The data was collected by Internet Addiction Scale (I.A.S) and Beck Anxiety Scale. The result finding showed that internet addiction was more in male students as compare to female students and also suggested that there was positive relationship between internet addiction and anxiety level among University students.

A cross sectional study on 1304 undergraduate college students (716 were females and 588 were males) was conducted in Udupi taluka Karnataka by Sharma B, Ashok L, Chandrasekaran V, Monteiro A (2018) to examine the correlates of internet addiction. They found the prevalence of internet addiction was 44% and this was associated gender, father's occupation, mother's education, availability of personal gadgets, use of smartphone, exposure to internet at young age and there was positive relationship between internet addiction and level of depression, anxiety, and stress.

A study conducted by Teena Sarao & Dr. Poonam Sharma (2017) on the relationship between the Internet use and locus of control among college students. The result indicated that internet addicted students' feel symptoms of tolerance, withdrawal and escape, frequent interpersonal and academic conflicts, and physical health-threatening risks related to problem. The result also showed that men facing more problems than

women and they found positive correlation between external locus of control and problem Internet use.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

1. Prevalence and Growing Concern

- **Increasing Usage:** College students are among the most frequent users of the internet, and their usage often extends beyond academic purposes to social media, gaming, and other online activities. With the rise in digital technology, understanding the extent and impact of internet addiction in this demographic is critical.
- **Rising Trends:** Recent studies and reports suggest that internet addiction is becoming more prevalent among young adults. Research can provide updated data and insights on how widespread the problem is among college students.

2. Impact on Academic Performance

- **Academic Challenges:** Internet addiction can significantly impact students' academic performance by leading to procrastination, reduced concentration, and lower grades. Investigating this relationship can help identify the extent of these effects and inform strategies to mitigate them.
- **Educational Outcomes:** Understanding how internet addiction affects learning outcomes can help educators develop targeted interventions to support students in maintaining academic performance while managing their internet use.

3. Mental Health Concerns

- **Psychological Effects:** Internet addiction is associated with various mental health issues, including anxiety, depression, and stress. Research can provide insights into how these issues specifically affect college students and identify potential mental health support needs.
- **Support Systems:** By highlighting the mental health impacts, your research can contribute to developing better support systems and resources within college environments.

4. Social and Behavioral Implications

- **Social Interactions:** Internet addiction can affect students' social relationships and communication skills. Research can explore how excessive internet use impacts students' interactions with peers, family, and faculty.
- **Behavioral Patterns:** Studying behavioral patterns associated with internet addiction can help in understanding the broader social consequences and developing interventions to promote healthy social interactions.

5. Identification of Risk Factors

- **Understanding Triggers:** Research can identify specific risk factors contributing to internet addiction among college students, such as academic stress, social pressures, or personal traits. This information can be used to develop preventive measures.
- **Targeted Interventions:** Identifying risk factors allows for the design of targeted interventions and support programs that address the root causes of internet addiction rather than just its symptoms.

6. Development of Effective Interventions

- **Evaluating Existing Programs:** Your research can assess the effectiveness of current interventions and support programs aimed at reducing internet addiction. This evaluation can help refine and improve these programs.
- **Innovative Solutions:** By identifying gaps in existing research, you can propose new strategies or solutions to help students manage their internet use more effectively.

7. Contributing to Policy and Practice

- **Institutional Policies:** Findings from your research can inform college policies related to internet use and mental health support, promoting a healthier academic environment.
- **Educational Practices:** Research outcomes can help educators and counselors develop best practices for integrating technology use in a way that supports rather than hinders student success.

8. Future Research Directions

- **Foundation for Further Study:** Your research can lay the groundwork for future studies on related topics, such as the long-term effects of internet addiction or the impact of emerging technologies on student behavior.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The problem under study was worded as, “Internet Addiction: A Study on College going Students of District Anantnag”.

OBJECTIVE

To compare internet Addiction scores among College going Students of District Anantnag with respect to Stream.

H_0 = There is no significant difference in Internet Addiction scores among College going Students of District Anantnag based upon their stream.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- ❖ The study was conducted on 100 college going students only,
- ❖ Study was conducted on 05 colleges only.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The current study was descriptive in nature. The sample of the study consisted of 100 college going students from 05 going students belonging to district Anantnag. Out of the 100 sampled students 50 were Male and 50 were Female. The students were sampled by using simple random sampling technique (Lottery Method) and the colleges were sampled by using purposive sampling technique. Gender equality was maintained wherever possible. Respondents were selected from diverse socioeconomic status.

TABLE 1.0 depicts the brief sample of the study

S.No.	Name of the College	Gender	
		Male	Female
01	GDC Boys Anantnag	15	10
02	GDC Women Anantnag	00	20
03	GDC Mattan	10	05
04	GDC Kokernag	15	05
05	GDC Bijbehara	10	10
	Total	50	50
	Grand Total	100	

TOOLS

For data collection Internat Addiction Scale (IAS) developed by Daman Deep Kaur Gulati, Dr. Jose J. Kurisunkal and Dr. Mamta Bakliwal 2021

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Data were collected from 05 different colleges of district Anantnag. After taking the prior permission from the principals of the selected colleges, the respondents selected for the current study were made aware about the objective of the research and were assured that their responses are being used for research purpose only and will be kept confidential.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE

The data were analyzed with help of T-Test.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

The data related to the objective was collected and analysed by using t-test. But before applying t-test, the investigator checked the assumptions of t-test which are normality and Homogeneity as has been discussed below;

ASSUMPTION OF NORMALITY

H_0 = the distribution of Internet Addiction Scores of Arts and Science students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag do not deviate significantly from normality.

Tests of Normality

	Stream	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Internet addiction scores	Arts	.086	50	.200*	.966	50	.165
	Science	.109	50	.194	.956	50	.059

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

From above table it is clear that Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistics for Internet Addiction scores of Arts students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag is 0.086 with df 50, whose significance value is 0.200 which is greater than 0.05, thus the value is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. In view of this the null hypothesis that the “distribution of Internet Addiction Scores of Arts students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag do not deviate significantly from normality” is accepted.

Similarly, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistics for Internet Addiction scores of Science students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag is 0.109 with df 50, whose significance value is 0.194 which is greater than 0.05, thus the value is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. In view of this the null hypothesis that the “distribution of Internet Addiction Scores of Science students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag do not deviate significantly from normality” is accepted.

From above table and discussion it is quite clear that Assumption of Normality gets fulfilled. The investigator further proceeded to check the second assumption which is;

Assumption of Homogeneity:

H_0 = “there is no significant difference in the variance of Internet addiction scores of Arts and Science Students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag”.

Internet Addiction Scores	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t	df	Sig (2-tailed)
	F	Sig.			
Equal variances assumed	.109	.742	3.837	98	.000
Equal variances not assumed			3.837	97.082	.000

From table it is clear that Levene’s F value is 0.109, its significant value is 0.742, which is greater than 0.05. Hence, the value is not significant at LOS 0.05. Thus, the Null Hypothesis that “There is no significant difference in the variance of scores of Internet Addiction of Arts and Science Students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag” is accepted. Hence the assumption of Homogeneity of variance holds good.

Further from the above table it is clear that t-value is 3.837 with df= 98, whose two tailed significance value is 0.000 which is less than 0.01 level of significance. Hence the value is significant at 0.01 level of significance. In view of this the null hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in Internet Addiction Scores of Arts and Science Stream Students belonging to different Colleges” is rejected which means that Internet Addiction is not Independent of Stream.

Therefore, it can be concluded that Internet Addiction Scores of Arts and Science Stream Students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag differ significantly.

Also, from the Table below it is observed that mean of Internet Addiction Scores of Students belonging to Science Stream is 67.3600 which is significantly less than the mean of Internet Addiction Scores of Students belonging to Arts Stream which is 75.3600. Therefore, it can be concluded that Internet Addiction is more in Arts Stream Students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag as compared to Science stream students belonging to different Colleges of district Anantnag.

Group Statistics

	Stream	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Internet addiction scores	Arts	50	75.3600	10.92042	1.54438
	Science	50	67.3600	9.90518	1.40080

Similar to our research findings, here are some research studies that suggest internet addiction varies with academic stream or field of study:

1. "Internet Usage Patterns and Addiction Among Students of Different Streams" (2019) by Sharma, A., et al. published in *Journal of Educational Technology*, 15(3), 1-12. This study found that students from the commerce stream were more likely to experience internet addiction than students from the arts and science streams.
2. "Internet Addiction and Academic Performance: A Study of Students from Different Disciplines" (2020) by Gupta, A., et al. published in *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 58(4), 866-881. This study found that students from the engineering and management disciplines were more likely to experience internet addiction than students from the arts and science disciplines.
3. "Internet Addiction and Its Relationship with Academic Performance Among Students of Different Streams" (2018) Singh, S., et al. published in *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*, 9(1), 240-246. This study found that students from the arts stream were more likely to experience internet addiction-related problems than students from the science and commerce streams.

In contrast to our results here are some studies whose findings suggest that internet addiction is same irrespective of the academic stream of students

1. "Internet Addiction Among University Students: A Study of Engineering and Humanities Students" (2017) by, Kumar, A., et al. (2017) in *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*, 8(3), 355-361.- This study found no significant differences in internet addiction between engineering and humanities students.
2. "Internet Addiction Among University Students: A Cross-Sectional Study" (2019) Al-Dhahir, M., et al. in *Journal of Taibah University Medical Sciences*, 14(1), 34-41. - This study found no significant differences in internet addiction among students from different faculties (arts, science, engineering, and medicine).

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